

Growth and Flowering Response of Two Species of Marigold (*Tagetes* spp.) to Water Stress

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ABSTRACT

Marigold (*Tagetes spp*) is among the high value potted flowers with an extended shelf life. It is commercially exploited for cut flowers. A pot experiment was conducted between February and May 2013 in the greenhouse of the College of Plant Science and Crop Production, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Nigeria to determine the growth and flowering response of two species of marigold: *Tagetes erecta* L. (African marigold) and *Tagetes patula* L. (French marigold) to water stress levels (0.5, 0.75 and 1 litre per plant per week). The experiment was laid out in a 2 x 3 factorial fitted in a completely randomized design with seven replicates. Data were collected on shoot height, number of leaves, canopy diameter, number of branches, number of flowers, and flower yield. Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using GENSTAT 12th edition while significant mean separation was done using least significance difference (LSD) at 5% level of probability (Wahua, 1999). The results showed that, French marigold was shorter, even though it elicited more number leaves, wider plant spread, more branches, higher number of flowers, and flower yield than African marigold. Irrigation at 0.75 and 1 L/week rates produced taller plant, more leaves, branches, flowers, and flower yield than plant that received 0.5 L/week. Both varieties irrigated at 0.75 and 1 L/week produced taller plant, more leaves, branches, flowers and flower yield than 0.5 L/week. However, there was no significant difference between Marigold species that received water at 0.75 and 1 L/week. In conclusion, irrigating either specie of marigold at 0.75 L per 7 kg of soil enhanced their growth and flower production.

Keywords: Water stress, *Tagetes patula*, *Tagetes erecta*, flower yield

INTRODUCTION

Marigold (*Tagetes* spp.) is an ornamental plant which belongs to the family Asteraceae. It is native to Mexico and Central America (Peres, 2007; Santos, 2013; *et al.*, 2015), and broadly divided into two groups namely, African (*Tagetes erecta* L.) and French (*Tagetes patula* L.) marigold. *T. erecta* grows generally tall and is known as tall marigold while *T. patula* is short and called dwarf marigold. Marigold habit of free flowering within a short duration to produce marketable flowers with wide spectrum of attractive colours, shapes, sizes, and extended shelf life has attracted the attention of flower growers. Marigold is reputed in organic agriculture for its inhibitory effects on

pathogenic bacteria, nematodes, fungi, and insecticidal properties (Scrivanti *et al.*, 2003; Rondon *et al.*, 2006; Xu *et al.*, 2011; Jain *et al.*, 2012; Dasgupta *et al.*, 2012; Santos *et al.*, 2015). The medicinal benefits of *Tagetes* spp have been evaluated and documented (Zulfigar, *et al.*, 2020).

Water is an important requirement in a lot of physiological processes including photosynthesis (Santosa *et al.*, 2010). Availability of water has a significant impact on the development and quality of ornamental plants (Crillo *et al.*, 2017; Zulfigar *et al.*, 2020). At the whole plant level, the effect of stress is usually perceived as a decrease in photosynthesis and plant growth, and is associated with alteration in carbon and

nitrogen metabolism (Cornic and Massacci, 1996). Climate change, population growth, increasing water demand, overexploitation of natural resources and environmental degradation have significantly degraded the world's freshwater resources. Many African countries experience either water stress (less than 1,700 m³ per capita per annum) or water scarcity (less than 1,000 m³ per capita per annum) or both (Stephen, 2009). This study was conducted to evaluate the response of marigold species to water stress and to determine the optimum rate of water that will support growth and flowering of Marigold.

Materials and methods

A pot experiment was conducted between January and May, 2013 in the greenhouse of the College of Plant Science and Crop Production, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta. The study site lies between Latitudes 7°13' - 7°14'N; Longitude 3°26' - 3°27'E and is located within a forest-savanna transition zone (Salako *et al.*, 2007). Prior to land preparation, pre-planting soil samples were randomly collected using soil auger within the depth of 0 – 20 cm. Soil samples collected were air-dried, ground, and sifted by a 2-mm sieve. Raised nursery beds (1 m x 2 m x 0.5 m) were sown with the two species (*Tagetes patula* and *Tagetes erecta*) of marigold seeds for four weeks and irrigated three times in a week. The following chemical analyses were done on the soil samples and compost using standard laboratory methods: soil pH (soil:water ratio of 1:25), organic carbon, total nitrogen, available P (using Bray-1 method), exchangeable basic cations; exchangeable acidity and effective cation exchange capacity (by summation method) (Okalebo, 2002). Particle size analysis was determined on the soil using Bouyoucos method (Bouyoucos, 1962). A seven-litre capacity perforated polythene pots were filled with amended topsoil.

The topsoil was amended with 10 t/ha poultry manure (Ojo *et al.*, 2012) three weeks before transplanting to aid mineralization. Transplanting was done four weeks after sowing at one seedling/pot. The pots were arranged in a 2 x 3 factorial fitted in a completely randomized design with seven replicates. Factors considered were Marigold species (*T. patula* and *T. erecta*) and water rate (0.5, 0.75 and 1 L per week). Data collection began two weeks after transplanting (WAT) at two-weeks interval for twelve weeks. Data were collected on plant height, number of leaves, canopy diameter, number of branches, number of flowers, and flower yield. Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using GENSTAT 12th edition (commercial version) while significant mean separation was done using the least significance difference (LSD) at 5% level of probability (Wahua, 1999).

Results and discussion

Varietal effects

The physical-chemical analysis showed that the soil textural class was sandy loam with a pH of 7.21, organic matter was low (0.94 %) than the critical level of 2.2 % recommended for annual crops in southwestern Nigeria (Adebusuyi, 1995), available P (19.88 mg/kg) compared to medium to high range of 20 – 100 g/kg (Horneck *et al.*, 2011), and total nitrogen was 0.10 % as compared to 2.0% which is considered suboptimum (Sobulo and Osinawe, 1987). It had medium magnesium (2.37 %: medium ranging between 0.5 – 2.5 % and low potassium (0.08 %: medium is between 0.4 – 0.6 % (Horneck *et al.*, 2011) as presented in Table 1. Poultry manure had low nitrogen (0.8 %), medium organic matter content (4.2 %) which is twice above the critical level, medium magnesium (1.2 %), low potassium (0.25 %) and phosphorus (18.81g/kg) as in Table 1. *Tagetes. erecta* produced taller plant compared with *T. patula* (Figure 1) but had fewer leaves (Figure 2), branches (Figure 3), flowers

(Figure 4) and lower flower yield (Figure 5). Number of flowers peaked at 10 WAT in both species. The varietal difference observed between the two marigold species could be as a result of genetic variations which agree with the findings of Asaduzzaman *et al.*, 2014.

Water stress

Water deficit is one of the major constraints on plant growth and development, causing reduction of crop productivity. To minimize water loss, among many adaptation strategies, plants close their stomata to reduce transpiration (Park, 2019). Shoot height (Figure 6), numbers of leaves (Figure 7), branches (Figure 8), flowers (Figure 9) and flower yield (Figure 10) were higher in marigold subjected to 0.75 and 1 L/week than 0.5 L/week. These results corroborate the study of Riaz *et al.* (2016) who reported that drought had significant effect on vegetative growth of *Conocarpus erectus*.

Interaction

Branching began at 2 and 4 weeks after transplanting in French and African marigold respectively. Flowers production started at 4 and 6 weeks after transplanting in both species respectively. There was no significant difference in the Marigold irrigated at 0.75 and 1 L/week with respect to vegetative growth and reproductive development. African and French marigold subjected to 0.75 and 1 L/week had more numbers of branches, leaves, flowers, and flower yield compared with 0.5 L/week. The least flower production was observed in African and French marigold subjected to 0.5 L/week of water. Drought is considered one of the major limiting factors affecting growth and productivity of ornamentals. It severely affects the morphological and physiological activities of the plants and hampers seed germination, root proliferation, biomass accumulation and quality of flowers. Drought stress was reported to reduce plant growth in previous studies (Eakes *et al.*, 1991; Niu and Rodriguez, 2009). In oleander, shoot growth, leaf area, and specific

Leaf mass were reduced under water deficit conditions, whereas root dry weight was unaffected by drought (Niu *et al.*, 2008). Water is the primary ecological element that threatens the survival and reproduction of plants. Mismanagement of irrigation water has adverse effects on the soil and crops (Ahmad and Ogunwole, 2009). Bradford and Hsiao (1982) suggested that plant growth may be inhibited at low water potential despite complete maintenance of turgor in the growing regions due to osmotic adjustment. Also, Kirnak *et al.* (2001) reported that shoot height of water stressed plants were smaller than the equivalent component in the well irrigated plants. The role of water as a solvent is critical in plant growth. It is required for physiological growth and translocation of absorbed nutrients (Samaila *et al.*, 2009). Insufficient water at any stage will impair growth and development just as too much of water impedes growth (Hanson *et al.*, 2001). Negative effects on growth and development of marigold subjected to 0.5 L/week could be as a result of metabolic alterations.

Conclusion

Irrigation at the rate of 0.75 and 1 L/week would support growth and flower yield of the African and French marigold. Irrigation at the rate of 0.75 L/week is adequate for the growth and yield of marigold in 7kg capacity pots. Subjecting marigold to water stress below 0.5 L/week could be lethargic.

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Table 1: Composition of the soil and poultry manure used in the experiment

Texturaclass	Soil	Poultry manure
Exchangeable bases (cmol/kg)		
Calcium	6.47	4.61
Magnesium	2.37	0.60
Potassium	0.08	0.25
Chemical propertie		
pH	7.21	6.70
Available Phosphoru (mg/kg)	19.88	18.81
Organic matter (%)	1.56	4.20
Total Nitrogen (%)	0.10	0.84
ECEC (cmol/kg)	9.10	
Particle size distribution		
Sand (%)	92.10	
Silt (%)	2.20	
Clay (%)	5.70	
Textural class	Sandy loam	

Figure 1: Shoot height of two marigold species
Vertical bars are LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)

Figure 2: Number of leaves of two marigold species
Vertical bars are LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)

Figure 3: Number of branches of two marigold species
Vertical bars are LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)

Figure 4: Number of flowers of two marigold species
Vertical bars are LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)

Figure 5: Flower yield of two marigold species
Vertical bar ia LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)

Figure 6: Shoot height of two marigold species
Vertical bars are LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)

Figure 7: Number of leaves of marigold species as affected by water stress
Vertical bars are LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)

Figure 8: Number of branches of marigold species as affected by water stress
Vertical bars are LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)

Figure 9: Number of flowers of marigold species as affected by water stress
Vertical bars are LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)

Figure 10: Flower yield of marigold species as affected by water stress
Vertical bar is LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)

Table 2: Interaction effects of variety and water stress on numbers of branches, leaves and flowers

Variety	Water rate (L)	Number of branches	Number of leaves	Number of flowers
African marigold	0.5	3.67	29.33	2.33
	0.75	6.33	48.00	5.33
	1	7.00	50.00	5.00
French marigold	0.5	7.67	50.67	3.67
	0.75	16.00	80.67	10.00
	1	16.33	83.00	9.00
LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)		2.10	5.95	2.18

Table 3: Interaction effects of variety and water stress on flower yield

Variety	Water rate (L)	Flower yield (t/ha)
African marigold	0.5	2.07
	0.75	5.59
	1	5.9
French marigold	0.5	2.57
	0.75	7.51
	1	7.92
LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)		2.1